

The Rehabilitation of Draa Naga Arboretum on the Forest of Djebel El Ouahch (North eastern-Algeria)

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Abstract

The aim of our work is to make a rehabilitation of Draa naga arboretum. Created in 1970 by the French colonial authorities, the arboretum covers 31 hectares in the north-eastern part of the forest of Djebel El Ouahch, formed by 77 plots. This arboretum has many assets as landscaped and pedagogical: it gathers 45 different species and has some remarkable species (red oak, Coulter pine, black pine). Since its creation in 1954, it has been the subject of experimental plantations of different hardwood and softwood species from different sources (America-Europe-Australia). Some work has been done since the launch: especially in 1983, the site received a complete silvicultural work (pruning-cleaning-plantation-stocking ...). In this study we will try to provide an arboretum management plan to make it in good condition.

Key words: Draa Naga Arboretum, Degradation, Rehabilitation, silvicultural work

Introduction

The arboretum of Draa Naga is located in forest of Djebel El Ouahch. In 1954 to 1967, 77 species of trees and shrubs were planted in an area of 30 ha (77 plots). This site has undergone many changes since its planting: fires, drought, frost, grazing. The arboretum was completely abandoned from 1980. Today the site degradation state is already very advanced (significant degradation of forested areas, many diebacks in trees, hydraulic system failure, lack of cleaning and access to land problems, water erosion in some plots ...). In this study, we will try to propose a rehabilitation plan of the arboretum to be useful to the forestry plan and scientifically, a hand and also make the welcoming and efficient site to educate a wide audience (public and school).

2. Materiel and methods

2.1. Presentation of the study area

The study area of Draa Naga arboretum (Djebel El Ouahch's forest) belongs administratively to the province of Constantine (Map 1) (Rached-Kanouni and al., 2014). It is located between longitude (X_1 : 6°42'5", X_2 : 6°42'30") and latitude (Y_1 : 36°20'45", Y_2 : 36°22'15"). The estimate terrain elevation above sea level is 950 meters. The relief is characterized by a low slope (3- 12%). The drainage system consists of a few ravines and collected by temporary flow regime. Its bioclimatic is semiarid to sub-humid. The climate of the region Draa Naga is characterized by a hot and dry summer, and a cold and wet winter with an annual rainfall of 700 mm. Soil type of forest station is silico-clay.

Map 1. Location of study area.

2.2. Methodology

Research all existing documentation such as:

- Topographic maps of the study area at 1/25.000 and turn them into digital format by scanning with a scanner.
- Pre-existing thematic maps and old maps of the arboretum.
- References (documents, reports and memory).

Several outputs on field were organized for data collection in each outing; we did a complete description of parcels visited. For each parcel, there was its current state (type of existing species and silvicultural work required).

Entering field data in GIS is made by the ARCGIS 10 software by creating an attribute table (HadeF and al., 2014). This phase is awarded for each plot multiple fields of information such as plot number, kind of existing species, the necessary work,...

After integrating all field data in the GIS, was undertaken in the development of several maps of the arboretum according to several criteria (species type, silvicultural work and proposals of rehabilitation).

3. Results and discussion

After 60 years of its inception, the arboretum is totally degraded. Downside risks are various such as, human activities, cold, drought, heat, frost and fire. Hardwoods have dominance over softwood (Map 2). The frequency of severe winters and minimum temperatures are important for foreign plants in the region. These winters have a drastic selection of the collections by eliminating all species that are not adapted to these extreme cold. Contrary, summer can be marked by the periods of very high temperatures. The fires have affected the arboretum in 1958 and caused a notable damage. Drought causes severe damage to spring planting as a result of the imbalance between transpiration and absorption. Snowfalls are relatively common in the arboretum, which cause serious damage. Table 1 shows the degraded plots.

Table 1: the degraded plot of Draa Naga arboretum

Plot	Species	description of the plot
6	<i>Melia Azedarach</i>	Degraded, invaded by eucalyptus
15	<i>Abies concolor</i>	Extinct
16	<i>Eucalyptus Brockcwayi</i>	Degraded , mix with Aleppo pine
17	<i>Pinus patula</i>	Degraded
30	<i>Pinus nigra</i>	Degraded
31	<i>Eucalyptus pauciflora</i>	Degraded
34	<i>Quercus coccinae</i>	Degraded , invaded by Aleppo pine
37	<i>Betula alba</i>	Degraded
42	<i>Alnus cordata</i>	Degraded
44	<i>Picea pungens</i>	Degraded
48	<i>Abies numidica</i>	Degraded
53	<i>Pinus brutia</i>	Degraded Invaded by eucalyptus
54	<i>Pinus pondérosa</i>	Degraded
56	<i>Cedrus deodora</i>	Degraded
57	<i>Pinus laricio</i>	Degraded
59	<i>Pinus laricio</i>	Degraded
61	<i>Pinus canariensis</i>	Degraded
62	<i>Cupressus dupreziana</i>	Degraded Invaded by eucalyptus
63	<i>Pinus ansignis</i>	Degraded
64	<i>Tétralinis articulata</i>	Degraded
65	<i>Cedrus Libani</i>	Degraded
66	<i>Morus alba</i>	Degraded Invaded by eucalyptus
67	<i>Morus nigra</i>	Degraded
68	<i>Larix decidua</i>	Degraded
69	<i>Taxus baccata</i>	Degraded and invaded by some kind of pinion pine
70	<i>Carya Illinoensis</i>	Degraded
71	<i>Argania spinoza</i>	Degraded Invaded by eucalyptus
75	<i>Abies numidica</i>	Degraded
76	<i>Abies numidica</i>	Degraded

Currently the arboretum contains 7 families of species:

- **Family Cupressaceae**, it has 5 kinds of Cypress represented by 5 species (arizona, hairless, lambert, sempervirens, Atlas).
- **Family Fabaceae** contains 2 species (*Acacia piconta*, locust false acacia), very low density because of fires.
- **Family Fagaceae**, has 4 species of oak trees (oak, rubra, afares, pedunculate), low density because of repeated fires, frost and drought.
- **Family of Myrtaceae** which includes 22 species which are: *Eucalyptus ovate*, *E. banaueriana*, *E. eleophora*, *E. stuartiana*, *E. sideroxylon*, *E. amygdalina*, *E. polyanthemus*, *E. pauciflora*, *E. dalrympleana*, *E. gunnii*, *E. cosmophloia*, *E. leucoxylon*, *E. blakelii*, *E. smithii*, *E. salmonphloia*, *E. maculata*, *E. robusta*, *E. astringens*, *E. méliodora*. This family is the most dominant contribution by the other families as it resisted almost all degradation factors
- **Family of Pinaceae** composed by 11 pins: Corsican pine, pine of canary, Pine brutia (parcelle19, 40), Pine brutia Greece, radiata (Insignis) exists in two parcels (28.72), Pine brutia of Cyprus jeffreyi, Ponderosa, Pinaster, appears low density because of the fires.
- **Family of Oleaceae**, includes 2 species, (Ash of America, Ash of Oregon), supports all soils, and supports winds, sensitive to frost. it is almost extinct because of repeated fires, or due to frost.
- **Family of Ulmaceae**, Features 1 species (Hackberry), almost disappeared because of fires repeated fires.

The following map shows the families that exists in the arboretum Daa Naga in 2014

Map 2. Distribution of families in the Draa Naga arboretum.

Rehabilitation actions

The purpose of the arboretum rehabilitation several forestry actions should be made to make it in a good condition.

Cleansing

The cleaning is the removal of competing trees in poor health for the benefit of objectives over story trees in the stand. This intervention involves young stands tall between 3 and 10 meters. The cleaning can:

- To obtain a good proportion of tree species in the stand.
- Eliminate subjects that threaten the well-developed trees.

Repopulation

The repopulation operation is done in plots with low density; this action is to make a reforestation species that exists in this plot.

Plantation

A planting operation is to set up plants from the nursery on a parcel prepared for this purpose. Planting ensures the renewal of forests. She prepares a quality stand when natural regeneration is missing.

Pruning

It is to remove partially or completely, some low living or dead or diseased branches at their junction point.

Coppicing

Coppicing (thinning out) is to reduce the density of the targeted species (target fuel) in favor of well-formed stems. It promotes growth in trunk diameter, crown development and improves the stability of trees.

The next maps (map 3 and 4) we abstract all necessary silvicultural work and the proposed species for the rehabilitation of the Arboretum.

Map 3. Silvicultural work for the rehabilitation of the Arboretum

Map 4. The species proposed for the rehabilitation of the arboretum.

Conclusion

It appears that the environment is under significant anthropogenic action that disrupted the balance of this ecosystem already weakened by intense pressure (overgrazing, repeated fires, deforestation, drought, frost ...). The behavior of plant species found today shows that some are threatened as endangered, *Sophora japonica*, *Quercus rubra*, while other extinct species (30 plots degraded) on the contrary, a good natural regeneration are observed Eucalyptus. Thus the presence of a wood (Asphodel, Diss and Calycotome ...) indicates a significant deterioration in the arboretum of Draa Naga. We answer this degradation by a rehabilitation program by silvicultural work on one hand and on the other by proposals for pardons, which are summarized as follows:

- To prohibit overgrazing (causing significant soil compaction, affecting the regeneration of species).
- Restocking vacuum with the introduction of existing species and which have good characteristics.
- Rehabilitation of the fence to prevent the passage of livestock.
- Monitoring and maintaining the health of the local biodiversity.

References

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